

AttackZoo: A Reproducible Testbed for the Execution of Attacks and the Generation of Network Traffic Datasets

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Abstract. *The recurring generation of network traffic datasets for cybersecurity research is constrained by fragmented experimental workflows, limited reproducibility, and restricted coverage of attack vectors. This paper presents AttackZoo, a reproducible testbed that integrates a containerized repository of 42 attacks categorized according to the MITRE ATT&CK framework and a web-based orchestration tool that automates the full cycle of execution, data collection, and consolidation. The pipeline incorporates traffic capture, log inspection, and feature extraction using multiple tools, producing structured and traceable datasets. By providing the broadest coverage of attacks, techniques, and tactics among existing testbeds, AttackZoo reduces the operational overhead of experiments and enables the systematic generation of comparable datasets, with all artifacts openly available.*

1. Introduction

The continuous advancement of research in areas such as network security and cybersecurity, especially in service scenarios, IoT, and heterogeneous environments, has increased the need for reproducible experimental methodologies for generating and analyzing traffic under controlled conditions [Fideles et al. 2025, Guo et al. 2024, Croft et al. 2023, Whang et al. 2023, Soares et al. 2021]. Despite the growing availability of tools, testbeds, and repositories, two central problems persist: the fragmentation of the experimental process and the limited scope and reach of existing solutions. In general, the available tools are vertically integrated, focused on specific technologies or protocols, and often cover a limited set of attacks¹. Hindering the conduct of comparable experiments and the generation of representative datasets. Furthermore, these solutions tend to require high operational effort, with low standardization, insufficient documentation for replication, and limited extensibility.

Additionally, generating realistic and up-to-date datasets remains a critical challenge [Ahmad et al. 2023, Kraust et al. 2025, Bragança et al. 2026]. Detection and analysis techniques are highly sensitive to changes in the ecosystem, such as service evolution, communication patterns, and adversarial strategies, which impose a relatively short validity period on datasets (e.g., 6 months). In this context, the absence of systematic and reproducible processes compromises both the comparability between studies and the validity of the results obtained [Pedrosa et al. 2024, Kraust et al. 2025, Bragança et al. 2026, Ahmad et al. 2023].

¹The vast majority of studies cover a maximum of 19 attacks [Sáez-de Cámara et al. 2024], with rare exceptions reaching 33 attacks [Neto et al. 2023]

This work addresses these limitations by proposing the integration of a repository of containerized attacks with a tool for orchestration and operation of the experimental cycle². The proposal unifies, within a single pipeline, the stages of attack execution, benign traffic generation, data capture, feature extraction, and *dataset* generation. Unlike existing approaches, which treat these stages in isolation, the system provides a standardized and automated operational workflow, reducing dependence on *ad hoc* scripts and manual interventions. In addition, the testbed was designed to incorporate new attacks in a simple and practical way, ensuring extensibility and sustainability.

As a result, the proposal enables reproducible execution of scenarios with low operational friction, while also expanding experimental coverage through an extensible repository of more than 40 attacks across 7 distinct categories. The generated *datasets* are structured and traceable, making it possible to associate data with the execution context and the parameters used. This favors more rigorous comparative analyses and contributes to the development of studies that are more consistent, robust, and aligned with current demands in the field.

2. Related work

Recent cybersecurity testbed literature highlights the need for controlled and sufficiently realistic experimental environments for attack evaluation, behavior observation, and countermeasure validation [Fideles et al. 2025, Guo et al. 2024, Croft et al. 2023, Whang et al. 2023, Soares et al. 2021]. Table 1 summarizes the main testbeds identified, highlighting their approaches and experimental focuses.

Table 1. Characteristics and coverage of related testbeds

Work	Testbed Characteristics						MITRE ATT&CK Coverage		
	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]	Attacks	Techniques	Tactics
[Kouril et al. 2014]	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	1	3	2
[Bernieri et al. 2017]	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	4	2	4
[Siboni et al. 2019]	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	5*	9	7
[Dhanapal and Nithyanandam 2021]	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	1	1	1
[Wlazlo et al. 2021]	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	3	4	4
[Jr. et al. 2021]	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	4	3	3
[Sáez-de Cámara et al. 2024]	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	19*	15	13
[Abdelrahman et al. 2023]	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	4	4	6
[Freitas et al. 2024]	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	4	4	4
[Katuri et al. 2024]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	2	1	1
[Huang et al. 2024]	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	8*	4	7
[Brito et al. 2025]	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	5*	8	6
This work	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	42	19	12

Legend: [1] *Support for real devices*, [2] *Support for emulated / virtualized devices*, [3] *IoT protocols*, [4] *General Ethernet application protocols*, [5] *Experiment replication instructions*, [6] *Accessible artifact repository available for public use*.

* The authors do not explicitly report the number of attacks; this value was inferred from the demonstrations described in the paper.

Note: *The complete mapping of techniques and tactics is available in the repository at <https://github.com/GT-IoTEdu/sbrc2026-ataques-acesso>.*

²Code & Data: <https://github.com/GT-IoTEdu/sbrc2026-ataques-acesso>

In general, two predominant approaches can be observed. Works based on real devices [Katuri et al. 2024, Abdelrahman et al. 2023] prioritize high fidelity and capture effects such as timing and operational noise, making them especially relevant in cyber-physical scenarios. In contrast, approaches based on emulation, virtualization, or containerization prioritize scalability, lower cost, and flexibility, thereby favoring the systematic repetition of experiments and reproducibility. These studies indicate the need to strike a balance between realism and experimental control.

With respect to scope, the literature is divided between vertical and horizontal proposals. The former target specific domains, such as Smart Grid, ICS (*Industrial Control Systems*), and SCADA (*Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition*) [Kraust et al. 2025, Wlazlo et al. 2021, Katuri et al. 2024, Bernieri et al. 2017]. The latter focus on general-purpose IP networks, exploring attacks such as DoS, MitM, scanning, and service exploitation. There is also growing interest in domestic and industrial IoT scenarios [Sáez-de Cámara et al. 2024, Jr. et al. 2021, Siboni et al. 2019, Firouzi et al. 2025, Huang et al. 2024], which are characterized by high heterogeneity and the use of lightweight protocols.

Despite these advances, important limitations remain. Most works do not provide artifact repositories or complete replication instructions. Moreover, no existing proposal simultaneously supports real devices, IoT protocols, general-purpose TCP/IP applications, and open artifact availability. The experimental process is often fragmented across multiple tools, and its scope is typically limited to a small set of attacks or protocols, hindering comparative analyses and compromising reproducibility.

In this context, this work proposes an operational integration based on three pillars: (i) explicit documentation of tools, techniques, and configurations; (ii) standardized and reproducible execution of diverse scenarios, including 42 attacks categorized according to MITRE ATT&CK³; and (iii) systematic data capture and organization for dataset construction. The proposal emphasizes the operationalization of the full experimental cycle, with open availability of artifacts such as code, containers, and configurations.

To better position our proposal with respect to the state of the art, Table 1 summarizes and compares existing testbeds in terms of attack coverage, techniques, and tactics. As shown in the table, most works present limited coverage, typically with a median of four attacks and a focus on restricted subsets of the attack cycle. In contrast, our approach covers 42 attacks distributed across 19 techniques and 12 tactics, spanning multiple stages from reconnaissance to impact. This broader coverage enables the generation of more representative *datasets* and supports more robust comparative experiments.

3. Architecture

AttackZoo is composed of two complementary components: a containerized attack repository and a web-based orchestration tool for managing the experimental cycle. Together, they address the two key limitations identified in the literature: fragmentation of the experimental process and limited scope of existing solutions. The repository provides broad and extensible coverage of attack vectors, while the orchestration tool integrates execution, data collection, and consolidation into a unified and standardized pipeline, eliminat-

³<https://attack.mitre.org/>

ing the need for *ad hoc* scripts and scattered manual interventions. Figure 1 presents an overview of the testbed architecture.

Figure 1. Overview of the testbed architecture

3.1. Attack repository

The attack repository is organized into three categories of Docker containers: attackers, target services, and clients. The attacker catalog comprises 42 attacks, each individually implemented in a single-purpose container using exclusively open-source tools. The adoption of individual containers maximizes isolation between scenarios, reduces interference across executions, and simplifies maintenance and future expansion of the catalog. Each new attack can be incorporated incrementally, without changes to the existing structure, as described in the specific technical documentation in the project repository.

The target services are provided by 7 dedicated containers, covering an intentional set of protocols and technologies. These include a web server with PHP and a database, SSH, Telnet, and SMB servers, an MQTT broker, a CoAP server, and a web server with a deliberately outdated SSL/TLS configuration. This diversity distinguishes our approach from most related works, which typically focus on a single protocol or application domain.

To interact with these services and compose realistic scenarios, benign traffic is generated by up to 10 instances of parameterizable clients. These clients can be configured in terms of target service, maximum number of requests, interval between accesses, and total execution time, enabling controlled, deterministic, and reproducible behavior. This design supports the construction of experimental baselines and the comparison of different executions, while also enabling the incorporation of more realistic usage profiles derived from public traces and benign traffic *datasets*. This allows synthetic generation to better approximate patterns observed in real environments.⁴

Each attacker is described by structured metadata, including identification, description, container image, supported parameters, security and usage notes, classification according to the MITRE ATT&CK framework, and contextualized warnings. These

⁴For example, public datasets of internal datacenter traffic [Polák et al. 2024] describe temporal stability and daily application traffic patterns in enterprise environments.

metadata directly feed the tool interface, which presents information about the attack, its usage, and the expected behaviour at each stage of execution. This documentation pattern ensures consistency in presentation and reduces the effort required to integrate new scenarios into the catalog.

3.2. Orchestration and control tool

The testbed operation tool was implemented as a web application using the Streamlit framework⁵ on Python, with the goal of eliminating the operational fragmentation common in approaches based on multiple scripts and isolated tools, where stages such as attack execution, traffic capture, feature extraction, and dataset generation are performed independently and require manual coordination. The tool centralizes the entire experimental cycle in a single interface, including attack selection and parameterization, controlled execution, real-time monitoring, and access to generated artifacts, as illustrated in Figure 3, with the interface shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Tool operation interface

Figure 3. Workflow of actions and functionalities of the testbed operation tool

Scenario execution is structured as a controlled pipeline that operationalizes the experimental cycle described previously. Upon user configuration, the application vali-

⁵<https://streamlit.io/>

dates input parameters, instantiates the corresponding containers in isolated Docker environments, monitors execution in real time, and persistently stores the resulting artifacts for subsequent analysis. The pipeline stages, including traffic capture, attack initiation, log collection, and controlled shutdown, are executed in a fixed order according to the scenario specification. This design ensures uniformity across executions and guarantees traceability of the generated data.

3.3. Implementation

The repository comprises a total of 51 containers: 42 attackers, 7 target servers, and 2 benign client models supporting multiple instances. All containers are based on publicly available images from Docker Hub⁶ and are defined through `Dockerfiles`, ensuring that any environment meeting the minimum requirements can fully replicate the testbed.

The integration between the repository and the tool adopts a modular architecture that favors extensibility and maintainability. To incorporate a new attack, it is sufficient to create the corresponding container and register it in `modules/registry.py`. From this registration onward, the tool automatically incorporates the new scenario into the web interface, generates the parameterization forms, orchestrates execution via Docker, performs traffic capture, feature extraction, and *dataset* generation, without requiring any additional manual intervention.

Packet capture uses `tcpdump` as the primary tool and `dumcap` as a *fallback*. Feature extraction from `.pcap` captures is performed in parallel by three complementary tools: `TShark`, the Python `Scapy` library, and the `NTLFlowLyzer` project [Shafi et al. 2025]. The use of three tools for the same purpose is intentional: each one has distinct constraints and particularities in flow attribute extraction, and parallel execution makes it possible to combine, in the consolidation stage, the attributes obtained from the three outputs by means of the `pandas` library, producing more complete and robust *datasets* than those obtained from any single tool alone.

4. First Results

The first experimental campaign evaluates the integrated repository and orchestration components through the systematic execution of catalog attacks under a uniform duration policy and a consistent collection and post-processing pipeline. In each run, attacks are executed, traffic is captured in `pcap` format, features are extracted using multiple tools, and derived *datasets* are generated as persistent artifacts.

Table 2 summarizes the scope and volume of data produced during an 8-hour continuous campaign, demonstrating the testbed’s ability to systematically operate the attack catalog and generate reusable outputs. The selected time window reflects practical computational constraints, as longer campaigns significantly increase data volume as well as processing and storage costs.

To ensure experimental feasibility, the campaign was conducted within a time window sufficient to exercise the full pipeline (execution, collection, extraction, and consolidation) without exceeding available computational resources. Nevertheless, the attack selection spans the full spectrum of the catalog, with at least one representative scenario

⁶<https://hub.docker.com/>

Table 2. Summary of the experimental campaign

Experiment configuration		Generated data	
Metric	Value	Metric	Value
Attacks executed	42	pcap captures	42
Categories covered	7	Total data volume	106.37 GB
Campaign duration	8 hours	Resulting dataset*	26.7 GB

* Consolidated dataset after feature extraction available at: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.31861711>

for each of the seven MITRE ATT&CK categories described in the metadata. This strategy ensures scenario diversity while maintaining comparability under a uniform experimental policy. In environments with greater computational capacity, the same architecture supports more extensive campaigns, with a larger number of repetitions and parameter combinations, thereby increasing statistical robustness.

The results demonstrate that the tool provides end-to-end orchestration of the experiment workflow, integrating attack execution, traffic capture, feature extraction, and *dataset* generation into a unified pipeline. Each execution constitutes an observable, standardized, and reusable unit. The uniform experimental policy ensures consistency of artifact, enabling cross-comparisons across attacks, categories, and target services. In addition, the persistence storage of pcap, extracted features, and *datasets* ensures reproducibility, auditability, and traceability.

Figure 4 presents an aggregated characterization of the captured traffic, highlighting diversity in protocols, ports, and temporal behavior under execution. TCP traffic predominates, reflecting the nature of the target services and attack scenarios, while UDP and ICMP appear with lower representation. The distribution across destination ports shows concentration on services such as 8080 and 1883 (web and IoT), along with others such as 80, 161, and 5683, indicating service heterogeneity. Temporal patterns exhibit high variability with frequent peaks, consistent with the interleaved execution of different attacks, while maintaining overall stability under the adopted experimental policy.

Figure 4. Traffic characterization during the experimental campaign

5. Availability and Demonstration Plan

The AttackZoo source code is available upon request from the authors via the project repository⁷, which includes installation and usage instructions, a demonstration video, and technical documentation in the `README.md`. The *testbed* can be deployed on *bare metal* or in a virtual machine and is entirely based on free and open-source software.

Execution requires Ubuntu 24.04 LTS, at least 4 CPU cores (x86/AMD64), 8 GB of RAM, 15 GB of storage, Internet access, and administrative privileges (e.g., `sudo`). Under these conditions, installation typically takes between 10–15 minutes, depending on computational resources and network conditions. The demonstration can be performed on a standard computer provided by the authors and covers installation, attack execution, traffic capture, and the post-processing pipeline, highlighting the integrated orchestration of the complete experimental cycle.

6. Conclusion and Future Work

This paper presented AttackZoo, a reproducible and extensible testbed that unifies the cybersecurity experimentation pipeline from scenario definition to dataset generation. The platform integrates a containerized repository with 42 attacks spanning 19 techniques and 12 MITRE ATT&CK tactics with an orchestration layer that automates execution, traffic capture, feature extraction, and data consolidation. It enables scalable, controlled experimentation, producing structured and traceable artifacts (*pcap*, features, datasets) that support consistent cross-scenario comparison. Compared to existing approaches, AttackZoo offers broader attack coverage and supports heterogeneous environments, including real devices, IoT protocols, and TCP/IP applications, while reducing overhead.

Aligned with the IoTedu vision, a key premise is enabling IDS capable of detecting zero-day threats through improved generalization. This requires exposure to diverse attack behaviors, as models lacking patterns such as lateral movement or multi-stage exploitation fail to detect novel variants. By evolving toward a repository with attacks mapped to MITRE ATT&CK, AttackZoo expands the behavioral space for training, providing a foundation for learning-based detection of evasive and previously unseen threats.

Future work directly addresses current limitations through rigorous scientific validation. We will quantify reproducibility via repeated executions and statistical analysis of network features, assess traffic fidelity against real-world datasets (e.g., CICIDS, UNSW-NB15) using formal similarity metrics, and evaluate dataset utility through IDS/IPS benchmarking and machine learning experiments, including cross-dataset generalization. We will also measure pipeline overhead and interference, and refine feature extraction by resolving inconsistencies across tools through explicit consolidation strategies.

We will further incorporate a systematic analysis of threats to validity, including limitations of containerized environments, synthetic traffic bias, attack realism, and concept drift, complemented by hybrid deployments to improve ecological validity. Finally, we will expand the attack catalog beyond 60 scenarios, enhance benign traffic generation using real traces, adopt a plugin-based architecture for standardized extensibility, integrate with complementary platforms such as *IoT-Zoo*, and release a fully public, versioned repository to ensure transparency, reproducibility, and community-driven validation.

⁷<https://github.com/GT-IoTEdu/sbrc2026-ataques-acesso>

A. Credentials for GitHub

For the exclusive purpose of evaluation by the reviewers and members of the Technical Committee on Artifacts (CTA), the GitHub repository⁸ is made available through the following credentials:

Username: sbrc26-attackzoo-eval

Password (for access): JEdRH5tAC_w7

Token (for cloning): 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

Access to this repository is strictly limited to the evaluation process of SBRC 2026. The provided credentials and all associated materials are confidential. Their use is restricted exclusively to local testing and execution by the authorized evaluators.

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⁸<https://github.com/GT-IoTEdu/sbrc2026-ataques>

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